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List of abbreviations

EU	European Union
GEN IV	Generation IV
GIF	Generation IV International Forum
IAEA	International Atomic Energy Agency
MIT	Massachusetts Institute of Technology
MTR	Materials Testing Reactor
NDT	Non-destructive Testing
SMR	Small Modular Reactors
T	Training Topic

1. Introduction

The rapid development of digital learning platforms has significantly expanded the availability of online education in engineering and materials science. Online courses, recorded lecture series and educational video materials provide opportunities for students, researchers and professionals to access specialised knowledge regardless of geographical location. These resources support continuous professional development and contribute to capacity building in highly specialised fields such as nuclear engineering and nuclear materials research.

A wide range of online educational materials is currently available in the field of materials science, including university courses, international training modules and open-access lecture series. These resources cover fundamental topics such as crystal structures, phase transformations, radiation effects, corrosion and mechanical behaviour of materials, as well as selected aspects of nuclear engineering and the research approaches applied in CONNECT-NM research lines: data management, manufacturing, qualification, irradiation, non-destructive testing / examinations, advanced characterization and multiscale modelling, application of artificial intelligence and machine learning for materials. They also address the various types of materials used in reactors: concrete, metallic materials, fuels, polymers, etc.

A significant proportion of these materials is hosted on official university platforms (e.g., MIT OpenCourseWare) and international educational portals such as the online learning system of the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA). These platforms provide structured courses, lecture notes and recorded lectures developed by recognised academic institutions and international organisations. In addition, a large number of educational videos and lecture series are available on open platforms such as YouTube, often complementing formal courses and supporting self-learning.

The variety of formats and platforms highlights the importance of systematically identifying and organising these resources to support education and training in nuclear materials of interest for CONNECT-NM partners.

In this context, the CONNECT-NM initiative aims to identify and compile existing online educational resources relevant to nuclear materials science. The overview presented in this deliverable summarises available courses and educational materials, identifies gaps in current training provision, and proposes new topics for online courses which could be helpful in material research.

2. Methodology

The identification of relevant online educational resources was carried out through a structured search and screening process focused on materials science topics relevant to nuclear engineering and nuclear energy systems. The objective of the methodology was to identify publicly accessible online courses, lecture series and educational materials covering the key topics listed above.

The first stage of the work consisted of reviewing educational materials available on the official websites of international organisations, universities and European projects. In particular, the online learning platform of the IAEA was systematically examined. All available online courses and webinar recordings were reviewed, and those related to nuclear materials, nuclear fuel,

modelling approaches and analytical techniques were identified and classified by their relevance to the topics addressed in the CONNECT-NM project.

In the second step, additional educational resources were identified through targeted searches on university educational platforms and open course repositories. Special attention was given to platforms that provide open educational materials such as recorded lectures, lecture notes and self-learning modules developed by universities and research institutions. These platforms often host structured courses that cover both fundamental and advanced aspects of materials science and nuclear engineering.

Further searches were carried out using general internet search engines to identify additional online courses and lecture materials available on educational portals, institutional websites and training platforms. The search process used combinations of specific keywords related to nuclear materials research and materials degradation in nuclear power plants.

The main keywords used during the search included:

a) Materials and degradation mechanisms

- nuclear materials
- nuclear fuels
- radiation damage
- material degradation in nuclear power plants
- thermal ageing
- corrosion and stress corrosion cracking
- structural materials, steels and concrete in nuclear systems
- materials of generation IV (Gen IV)
- small modular reactors

b) Research approach:

- data management
- modelling and simulation
- machine learning/ artificial intelligence in nuclear materials
- manufacturing
- joining
- non-destructive testing (NDT) techniques

In addition to standard internet searches, educational content was also identified through systematic searches of online video platforms such as YouTube, where many universities and researchers publish recorded lectures and educational series related to materials science and engineering. These materials often complement formal university courses and provide accessible explanations of fundamental concepts, experimental methods and modelling approaches used in materials research.

To ensure broader coverage, advanced search tools, including AI-based information retrieval systems, were also employed. In total, a representative set of online educational resources was identified and screened, focusing on courses that are accessible, relevant to nuclear materials and suitable for self-learning or professional training.

All identified materials were subsequently screened and evaluated according to several criteria, including relevance to nuclear materials research, accessibility of the content, educational value and clarity of authorship or institutional affiliation. Only resources meeting

these criteria were included in the final dataset. The selected resources were then categorised into thematic groups corresponding to the main research areas addressed in the CONNECT-NM project, by family of materials on the one hand and on research approaches on the other hand.

In total, approximately 80 online courses and educational videos were identified and analysed, forming the dataset that serves as the basis for the overview presented in this deliverable.

3. Database of Identified Online Courses and Educational Resources

This chapter presents the database of identified online educational resources relevant to nuclear materials science and engineering. The database includes online courses, lecture series, webinars and educational videos covering topics related to materials used in nuclear systems.

To provide a clear overview, the identified resources were organised into thematic categories corresponding to the main research areas relevant to the CONNECT-NM project. These include:

- 3.1 Materials and degradation mechanisms
 - 3.1.1 General properties of materials
 - 3.1.2 Metallic structural materials
 - 3.1.3 Nuclear fuels
 - 3.1.4 Concrete
- 3.2 Research approaches
 - 3.2.1 Data management and ontologies
 - 3.2.2 Modelling and simulation
 - 3.2.3 Manufacturing and joining
 - 3.2.4 Non-destructive testing
 - 3.2.5 Advanced characterization techniques

Each entry in the database contains basic information about the educational resource, including the course title, providing institution, format, target audience, duration and a short description of the content. Direct links to the educational materials are also included to enable access to the sources. The identified educational resources are summarised in the following tables.

3.1. Materials and Degradation Mechanisms

3.1.1 General properties of materials

Engineering & Technology: Materials science course

Field	Information
Course title	E-content: Engineering & Technology: Materials science course
Provider / institution	Engineering & Technology Educational Channel, Worldwide
Format	Online lectures (video - YouTube)
Year / period	From 2000
Target audience	Engineering students
Price / fee	Free
Lecturers / organisers	More academic tutors
Workload / duration	Approx. 30 – 40 minutes
Topic category	General properties of materials
Short description / syllabus	Materials science concepts relevant for nuclear energy systems: introduction to materials science, atomic structure, bonding and crystal structures of materials, crystal defects, diffusion and phase transformations in materials, solidification processes, mechanical behaviour of materials, mechanical testing and characterization of material properties, processing and manufacturing of engineering materials, corrosion, degradation and surface protection of materials. Functional and advanced materials for engineering and energy applications.
Type of access	Open access (self-study)
Link	https://www.youtube.com/@e-contentengineeringtechno251/search?query=materials%20science

Introduction to Materials Science for Nuclear Engineering

Field	Information
Course title	Introduction to Materials Science for Nuclear Engineering
Provider / institution	Cambridge Nuclear Engineering, UK
Format	Online lectures (video – YouTube)
Year / period	From 2021
Target audience	Engineering students
Price / fee	Free
Lecturers / organisers	Dr. Miles Stopher
Workload / duration	4 independent lectures (~50 min)
Topic category	Nuclear materials
Short description / syllabus	Lecture introducing materials science concepts relevant to nuclear engineering, including radiation effects, structural materials and their behaviour in nuclear systems. Lesson about crystallography, plastic deformation and precipitates.
Type of access	Open access (self-study)
Link	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bmruuAJSvw4 https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6xWNVXh1uAA https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BR7mWGEykts https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VBarHV4KS-A

Introduction to Nuclear Engineering and Ionizing Radiation

Field	Information
Course title	Introduction to Nuclear Engineering and Ionizing Radiation (MIT 22.01)
Provider / institution	Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT open course), USA
Format	Online lecture series (full recorded course, video)
Year / period	From 2016
Target audience	Undergraduate engineering students
Price / fee	Free
Lecturers / organisers	Prof. Michael Short
Workload / duration	~34 lectures (~19 hours total)
Topic category	Nuclear structural materials / nuclear engineering fundamentals
Short description / syllabus	Introductory course covering nuclear science and engineering applications, including nuclear models, radioactivity, nuclear reactions, interaction of radiation with matter, radiation detection and shielding, and fundamentals of nuclear energy systems.
Type of access	Open access (self-study)
Link	https://ocw.mit.edu/courses/22-01-introduction-to-nuclear-engineering-and-ionizing-radiation-fall-2016/ Radiation damage (Lecture 27): https://ocw.mit.edu/courses/22-01-introduction-to-nuclear-engineering-and-ionizing-radiation-fall-2016/resources/nuclear-materials2014radiation-damage-and-effects-in-matter/ Nuclear materials (Lecture 29): https://ocw.mit.edu/courses/22-01-introduction-to-nuclear-engineering-and-ionizing-radiation-fall-2016/resources/nuclear-materials-science-continued/

Materials in Nuclear Engineering

Field	Information
Course title	Materials in Nuclear Engineering (MIT 22.14)
Provider / institution	Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT open course), USA
Format	Online presentations (pdf documents)
Year / period	Recorded in 2015
Target audience	Undergraduate students
Price / fee	Free
Lecturers / organisers	Prof. Michael Short
Workload / duration	Semester course – 6 presentations
Topic category	Nuclear materials
Short description / syllabus	Behaviour of materials in nuclear reactors, including radiation damage, corrosion, mechanical degradation, phase diagram, free energy, as well as various materials such as steels and fuels
Type of access	Open access (self-study)
Link	https://ocw.mit.edu/courses/22-14-materials-in-nuclear-engineering-spring-2015/pages/lecture-notes/

Introduction to Materials Science and Engineering

Field	Information
Course title	Introduction to Materials Science and Engineering
Provider / institution	Materials Science educational channel
Format	Video Lectures, YouTube
Year / period	From 2018
Target audience	Bachelor's and Master's students in materials science, mechanical engineering, nuclear engineering and related fields
Price / fee	Free
Lecturers / organisers	Prof. Rajesh Prasad (Indian Institute of Technology Delhi)
Workload / duration	Individual lectures typically 10–40 min
Topic category	Materials / Materials science fundamentals
Short description / syllabus	The video lecture series introduces fundamental concepts of materials science and engineering. Topics include the classification of materials, crystal structures and lattices, defects in solids, diffusion, solid solutions, phase transformations and mechanical properties of materials. The lectures also explain the relationship between processing, structure, properties and performance of materials and illustrate how microstructure influences engineering behaviour.
Type of access	Open access (self-study)
Link	https://www.youtube.com/@introductiontomaterialsscience

Material Science and Metallurgy (YouTube profile of Dr. Patil)

Field	Information
Course title	Material Science and Metallurgy
Provider / institution	Dr. Sagar D. Patil
Format	Online video presentations, YouTube
Year / period	From 2019
Target audience	Students of material engineering
Price / fee	Free
Lecturers / organisers	Dr. Sagar D. Patil (Sharad Institute Of Technology, India)
Workload / duration	Short lectures, approx. 25 min/video
Topic category	Materials science / Structural materials
Short description / syllabus	The video series introduces materials science and metallurgy. Lectures explain the basic concepts of materials, their properties, microstructure and mechanical behaviour. The course also covers topics such as crystal structure, defects in crystals, composite materials and basic metallurgical processes.
Type of access	Open access (self-study)
Link	https://www.youtube.com/@DrSagarDPatil/videos

Fracture and Fatigue

Field	Information
Course title	Fracture and Fatigue (MIT 3.35)
Provider / institution	Massachusetts Institute of Technology (Department of Materials Science and Engineering)
Format	Online presentations
Year / period	From 2003
Target audience	Graduate students in materials science and mechanical engineers interested in fracture mechanics and fatigue of materials
Price / fee	Free
Lecturers / organisers	Prof. S. Suresh, prof. D.M. Parks, T. Hanlon
Workload / duration	Semester course; approx. 2 lectures per week (≈ 1.5 h per session)
Topic category	Nuclear structural materials / Mechanical behaviour of materials
Short description / syllabus	The course investigates linear elastic and elastic-plastic fracture mechanics, as well as the fatigue behaviour of engineering materials. Topics include fracture mechanisms in metals, ceramics, polymers and composites; crack initiation and propagation; microstructural effects on fracture; interface fracture mechanics; toughening mechanisms; fatigue crack growth; stress-life and strain-life fatigue approaches; corrosion fatigue; and case studies of structural failures in engineering components.
Type of access	Open access (self-study)
Link	https://ocw.mit.edu/courses/3-35-fracture-and-fatigue-fall-2003/resources/total_life/

Other educational videos

Video title	Author	Topic	Link
Case Studies of Corrosion Failures	Hooke College of Applied Sciences, USA	Basics of crack propagation, fracture behaviour and structural failure	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3yGo-OU9bDU
Materials Science for Nuclear Energy Applications	K. Elsayed (Texas AM University, USA)	Basic knowledge in material engineering	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7i08Q_eqVFA
Interaction of Nuclear Radiation with Matter	Dibyajyoti Das (Hansraj College)	Understanding the different kinds of interactions of nuclear particles with matter	https://youtu.be/Ara0eTv02No?si=k05OdVO94r0NZenM
Nuclear Radiation & Radiation Damage to Materials	Kristine E. Zeigler (Vanderbilt University, USA)	Radiation effects in materials, defect formation, irradiation damage mechanisms in nuclear systems	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=d3k6muxeuNw
Pipeline Integrity: Stress Corrosion Cracking (SCC) and Corrosion Fatigue	Yuelfi Engineering channel, USA	Stress-strain relationships, elastic and plastic deformation of materials	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pr3-WuLDtRg
Stress Corrosion Cracking – Determination and Identification	M. J. Perrocone (RJ Lee Group, USA)	Mechanisms of stress corrosion cracking and environmental degradation of metals	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RABxoMjI4eQ
Understanding Material Strength, Ductility and Toughness	The Efficient Engineer channel, UK	Mechanical properties of materials, including yield strength, ductility and fracture toughness	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WSRqJdT2COE
Thermal Fatigue Damage Mechanisms (Mechanical and Metallurgical Failure Mechanisms)	Yuelfi Engineering channel, USA	Fatigue, critical factors and monitoring	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4_uVsPloxLQ

3.1.2 Metallic structural materials

Webinar Series about GEN IV structural materials

Field	Information
Course title	Webinar Series about GEN IV structural materials
Provider / institution	Generation IV International Forum (GIF)
Format	Online webinar (GIF channel, YouTube playlist)
Year / period	From 2018
Target audience	Researchers, nuclear engineers, materials scientists, students
Price / fee	Free
Lecturers / organisers	GEN IV and material experts
Workload / duration	4 independent lectures, between 1 – 2 hours
Topic category	Structural materials of GEN IV
Short description / syllabus	Materials challenges, advanced manufacturing, development of structural alloys for Gen IV reactors under extreme irradiation, temperature and corrosion conditions.
Type of access	Open access
Link	Materials Challenges for Generation IV Reactors: https://youtu.be/l_RVB8G8Ero?si=P1nQt3GPmfuOmF53 Opportunities for Gen IV Reactors Designers through Advanced Manufacturing Techniques: https://youtu.be/ChhCuiHKg3w?si=WabiEP57vzv1NiPD Development of Nanosized Carbide Dispersed Alloys for Gen IV Systems: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-GMkAd_TkLo Development of an Austenitic Martensitic Gradient Steel by Additive Manufacturing: https://youtu.be/a9DPjZ6_Ufs?si=rU7InGZk2znJ0z-O

Webinar: Steel and Metal Alloys 101

Field	Information
Course title	Park Systems Webinar: Steel and Metal Alloys 101
Provider / institution	Park Systems
Format	Online presentation
Year / period	From 2018
Target audience	Nuclear engineers, students
Price / fee	Free
Lecturers / organisers	Prof. Rigoberto C. Advincula (CWR University, Ohio)
Workload / duration	Up to 1 hour
Topic category	Steels and metal alloys
Short description / syllabus	Material classification, steel production, manufacturing, properties, impact of alloying elements
Type of access	Open access
Link	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1dj27Xkk3ts

Metal Technology Webinar

Field	Information
Course title	Metal Technology Webinar
Provider / institution	Institution of Mechanical Engineers – ImechE, London
Format	Online webinar
Year / period	From 2021
Target audience	Researchers, nuclear engineers, students
Price / fee	Free
Lecturers / organisers	Institution of Mechanical Engineers - IMechE
Workload / duration	Up to 85 minutes
Topic category	Metallurgy and metals
Short description / syllabus	Fundamental of Metallurgy, casting, heating, colling, carburising, nitriding and ageing, crystal structure, etc.
Type of access	Open access
Link	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cPYGDlclXAA

3.1.3 Nuclear fuels

Fuels and fuel cycle for Generation IV reactors

Field	Information
Course title	Decoding the fuel cycle
Provider / institution	PUMMA European project
Format	Recordings of presentations of four PUMMA workshops
Year / period	From 2024
Target audience	Students, researchers, nuclear engineers
Price / fee	Free
Lecturers / organisers	Researchers involved in PUMMA project:
Workload / duration	~25 hours in 60 videos between 6 min and 1h
Topic category	Fuels for GENIV reactors
Short description / syllabus	Fuel cycle scenarios, fuel qualification and codes, properties fuels, mixed oxide fuels, spent fuels
Type of access	Public
Link	https://pumma-h2020.eu/mooc-decoding-the-fuel-cycle

Online training on Fuel Performance Codes

Field	Information
Course title	Online training on Fuel Performance Codes
Provider / institution	OperaHPC project
Format	Online videos and self-assessment
Year / period	From 2026
Target audience	Students, researchers, nuclear engineers
Price / fee	Free
Lecturers / organisers	Researchers from Polimi, EPFL, CEA involved in OperaHPC project
Workload / duration	1,5 - 2 hours
Topic category	Fuels for GENII-III reactors
Short description / syllabus	Nuclear fuel rod behaviour, fission gas behaviour, simulation of fuel behaviour, open source SCIENTIX and OFFBEAT fuel performance codes
Type of access	Public
Link	https://www.operahpc.eu/education-training

Nuclear Front End Webinar Series – Fuel Materials for Fast Reactors

Field	Information
Course title	Nuclear Front End Webinar Series 1.6 – Results of the Coordinated Research Project on Fuel Materials for Fast Reactors
Provider / institution	International Atomic Energy Agency (eLearning)
Format	Online course (self-paced module, video presentation)
Year / period	From 2025, available continuously (self-paced online course)
Target audience	Researchers, nuclear engineers
Price / fee	Free
Lecturers / organisers	Dr. K. S. Sim, Dr. N. Waeckel and Dr. J. Zhang
Workload / duration	1,5 hours
Topic category	Nuclear fuel materials
Short description / syllabus	Webinar presenting results of a coordinated research project on fuel materials and cladding behaviour for sodium-cooled fast reactors and related modelling and testing approaches.
Type of access	Public after registration – Access through registered account
Link	https://www.iaea.org/online-learning/courses/2461/nuclear-front-end-webinar-series-12-nuclear-fuel-reliability-and-performance-in-water-cooled-reactors

General Fuel Overview, Design, Fuel Fabrication, Surveillance and Qualification Process

Field	Information
Course title	General Fuel Overview, Design, Fuel Fabrication, Surveillance and Qualification Process
Provider / institution	International Atomic Energy Agency (eLearning)
Format	Online course (self-paced module, video presentation)
Year / period	Available continuously (self-paced online course)
Target audience	Nuclear engineers, researchers
Price / fee	Free
Lecturers / organisers	IAEA experts
Workload / duration	~2–3 hours
Topic category	Nuclear fuel materials
Short description / syllabus	Introduction to nuclear fuel design, fabrication processes, fuel qualification procedures and surveillance of fuel behaviour during reactor operation.
Type of access	Public after registration – Access through registered account
Link	https://www.iaea.org/online-learning/courses/1546/module-1-general-fuel-overview-design-fuel-fabrication-surveillance-and-qualification-process

Nuclear Fuel for Advanced Reactors

Field	Information
Course title	Nuclear Fuel for Advanced Reactors
Provider / institution	International Atomic Energy Agency (eLearning)
Format	Online course (self-paced module, video presentation)
Year / period	Available continuously (self-paced online course)
Target audience	Nuclear engineers and researchers
Price / fee	Free
Lecturers / organisers	IAEA experts
Workload / duration	~2–3 hours
Topic category	Nuclear fuel materials
Short description / syllabus	Overview of nuclear fuel technologies for advanced reactor concepts, including fast reactors and Generation IV systems.
Type of access	Public after registration – Access through registered account
Link	https://www.iaea.org/online-learning/courses/1846/module-3-nuclear-fuel-for-advance-reactors

Conventional Nuclear Fuel for Thermal Reactors

Field	Information
Course title	Conventional Nuclear Fuel for Thermal Reactors
Provider / institution	Online course (self-paced module, video presentation)
Format	Available continuously (self-paced online course)
Year / period	Ongoing
Target audience	Nuclear engineers and students
Price / fee	Free
Lecturers / organisers	IAEA experts
Workload / duration	~2–3 hours
Topic category	Nuclear fuel materials
Short description / syllabus	Course covering conventional fuel designs used in thermal reactors, including UO ₂ fuel, cladding materials and fuel performance considerations.
Type of access	Public after registration – Access through registered account
Link	https://www.iaea.org/online-learning/courses/1726/module-2-conventional-nuclear-fuel-for-thermal-reactors

Advanced Nuclear Fuel for Thermal Reactors

Field	Information
Course title	Advanced Nuclear Fuel for Thermal Reactors
Provider / institution	International Atomic Energy Agency (eLearning)
Format	Online course (self-paced module, video presentation)
Year / period	Available continuously
Target audience	Nuclear engineers and researchers
Price / fee	Free
Lecturers / organisers	IAEA experts
Workload / duration	~2–3 hours
Topic category	Nuclear fuel materials, thermal reactors, commercial fuel
Short description / syllabus	Course on advanced fuel technologies developed for thermal reactors, including accident-tolerant fuels and advanced cladding materials.
Type of access	Public after registration – Access through registered account
Link	https://www.iaea.org/online-learning/courses/1847/module-4-advanced-nuclear-fuel-for-thermal-reactors

Nuclear Fuel Reliability and Performance in Water-Cooled Reactors

Field	Information
Course title	Nuclear Fuel Reliability and Performance in Water-Cooled Reactors
Provider / institution	International Atomic Energy Agency (eLearning)
Format	Online course (self-paced module, video presentation)
Year / period	Available continuously
Target audience	Nuclear engineers and researchers
Price / fee	Free
Lecturers / organisers	IAEA experts
Workload / duration	~2–3 hours
Topic category	Nuclear fuel materials, manufacturing development, burn-up, new fuel, recycling
Short description / syllabus	Webinar discussing fuel performance and reliability in water-cooled reactors, operational experience and mechanisms influencing fuel degradation.
Type of access	Public after registration – Access through registered account
Link	https://www.iaea.org/online-learning/courses/2461/nuclear-front-end-webinar-series-12-nuclear-fuel-reliability-and-performance-in-water-cooled-reactors

Webinar Series about GEN IV fuels

Field	Information
Course title	Webinar Series about GEN IV fuels
Provider / institution	Generation IV International Forum (GIF)
Format	Online webinar (GIF channel, YouTube playlist)
Year / period	From 2018
Target audience	Researchers, nuclear engineers, materials scientists, students
Price / fee	Free
Lecturers / organisers	GEN IV and material experts
Workload / duration	Between 1 – 2 hours
Topic category	Fuels for GEN IV reactors
Short description / syllabus	Performance assessment and behaviour of nuclear fuels under irradiation, including design, testing and operational reliability in advanced reactors.
Type of access	Open access
Link	Performance Assessments for Fuels and Materials for Advanced Nuclear Reactors: https://youtu.be/71iNkknztJU?si=nBiXBLwz2TZmALsM Materials Challenges for Generation IV Reactors: https://youtu.be/l_RVB8G8Ero?si=P1nQt3GPmfuOmF53 Metal Fuel for Prototype Gen IV Sodium Cooled Fast Reactors: https://youtu.be/EljDnzsuzY0?si=WtmDb_DDaHJougyU

3.1.4 Concrete

Nuclear Decommissioning in the Context of Sustainability and Circular Economy

Field	Information
Course title	Nuclear Decommissioning in the Context of Sustainability and Circular Economy
Provider / institution	International Atomic Energy Agency
Format	Online webinar
Year / period	Ongoing webinar series
Target audience	Nuclear engineers, waste management specialists, researchers and regulators
Price / fee	Free
Lecturers / organisers	IAEA experts and invited specialists
Workload / duration	~1–2 hours
Topic category	Concrete / Decommissioning / Waste management
Short description / syllabus	The webinar focuses on the management of concrete structures during nuclear decommissioning, including dismantling, decontamination, recycling and reuse of concrete materials. It highlights sustainability aspects and circular economy approaches in NPP infrastructure.
Type of access	Open access
Link	https://www.iaea.org/online-learning/courses/1315/nuclear-back-end-webinar-series-112-nuclear-decommissioning-in-the-context-of-sustainability-and-circular-economy

Concrete Technology and Codes

Field	Information
Course title	Concrete Technology and Codes
Provider / institution	U.S. NRC
Format	Pdf support of onsite training
Year / period	Since 2012
Target audience	Students, nuclear engineers, researchers and regulators
Price / fee	Free
Lecturers / organisers	Experts from the Portland Cement Association (PCA)
Workload / duration	39 self-paced lectures
Topic category	Concrete
Short description / syllabus	Fundamentals, cementitious materials, fabrication, specifications, degradation, durability, evaluation, nuclear codes
Type of access	Open access
Link	https://www.nrc.gov/docs/ML1215/ML12153A317.html

Other educational videos

Video title	Author	Topic	Link
Mod-01 Lec-34 Basic non-destructive testing for concrete structures	NPTEL, India	Overview of main NDT techniques used in industrial inspection	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JGQnbwxPiFA
Non-Destructive Tests (NDT) on Concrete	Technical Training Channel, India	Non-destructive evaluation using ultrasonic pulse velocity testing	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pblvdy71cEo

3.2 Research approaches

3.2.1 Data management and ontologies

Bringing Data to Life: Data Management

Field	Information
Course title	Bringing Data to Life: Data Management
Provider / institution	EMBL-EBI
Format	Online course
Year / period	Ongoing
Target audience	Researchers, PhD students, data stewards and professionals working with scientific data
Price / fee	Free
Lecturers / organisers	EMBL-EBI training team
Workload / duration	Short course (typically a few hours to 1–2 days depending on format)
Topic category	Data management / Ontologies
Short description / syllabus	The course introduces key principles of research data management, including data organisation, metadata standards, FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), and best practices for ensuring data quality, sharing and reuse across scientific communities.
Type of access	Open access
Link	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/training/online/courses/bringing-data-to-life-data-management/

Ontologies, Graphs & Deep Learning for AI

Field	Information
Course title	Ontologies, Graphs & Deep Learning for AI
Provider / institution	YouTube / Data Science Initiative
Format	Online video lecture
Year / period	Not explicitly specified (recent seminar-style content)
Target audience	Researchers, PhD students and professionals in AI, data science, knowledge graphs and semantic technologies
Price / fee	Free
Lecturers / organisers	Not explicitly specified (seminar speaker format)
Workload / duration	Short lecture (~1 hour typical for similar seminars)
Topic category	Data management / Ontologies / AI
Short description / syllabus	The seminar explores the intersection of ontologies, knowledge graphs and deep learning, focusing on how structured semantic representations can enhance AI systems. It covers concepts such as graph-based data modelling, reasoning over knowledge graphs and integration with machine learning approaches. These topics are central to modern AI systems combining symbolic and data-driven methods.
Type of access	Open access
Link	https://www.classcentral.com/classroom/youtube-dsi-seminar-ontologies-graph-deep-learning-ai-343332

Other educational videos

Video title	Author	Topic	Link
Using Ontologies to Guide Knowledge Graph Creation from Unstructured Data	Neo4j (webinar speaker - Jessus Barrasa)	Use of ontologies for building knowledge graphs from unstructured data; integration with AI and NLP	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RYuw4oq0G84
Virtual Knowledge Graph Approach Webinar	Research / industry webinar (speakers Alessandro Mosca, Free University of Bozen-Bolzano)	Integration of heterogeneous data sources using ontologies and virtual knowledge graphs	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HlmmxApfMIA
Knowledge Graphs Created through Machine Learning	Workshop (data science / Neo4j context)	Building knowledge graphs from text using machine learning and NLP techniques	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=T4DR4UNh8ag
Knowledge Graphs and Semantic Technologies Course	Academic lecture series (speaker - C.J. Sullivan - Data science Advocate)	Fundamentals of RDF, OWL, semantic web, ontologies and reasoning	https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PL6YcXD049UlcJYHYxW6RVC9hy-6LLtqy6
Ontologies and OWL (PhD Lecture)	Academic lecture (Politecnico di Torino)	Formal ontology modelling, OWL language and semantic reasoning	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=x8Lk0pjuqC4
How to Design Your Own Ontology	Ontology engineering lecture (Prof. H. Sack, M.A. Tan)	Principles of ontology design and modelling of real-world entities	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=twEPP-M8iqc
Ontology-First Knowledge Graphs	Industry talk (A. Bertails)	Ontology-driven design of knowledge graphs and semantic systems	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CbbPwy1p6QE

3.2.2 Modelling and simulation

Atomistic Modelling of Radiation Damage in Nuclear Systems

Field	Information
Course title	Atomistic Modelling of Radiation Damage in Nuclear Systems
Provider / institution	International Atomic Energy Agency (eLearning)
Format	Online course (self-paced module, video presentation)
Year / period	Available continuously
Target audience	MSc, PhD students, researchers
Price / fee	Free
Lecturers / organisers	IAEA experts
Workload / duration	~10–20 hours
Topic category	Nuclear structural materials – irradiation damage modelling
Short description / syllabus	Course on atomistic modelling of radiation damage processes, defect production, displacement cascades and simulation approaches for nuclear materials
Type of access	Public after registration – Access through registered account
Link	https://www.iaea.org/online-learning/courses/1207/atomistic-modelling-of-radiation-damage-in-nuclear-systems

Computational Nuclear Science and Engineering

Field	Information
Course title	Computational Nuclear Science and Engineering
Provider / institution	International Atomic Energy Agency (eLearning)
Format	Online self-learning module (video lectures, presentations, learning materials)
Year / period	Available continuously (self-paced online course, presentations)
Target audience	Students, nuclear engineers, researchers, staff of nuclear utilities, technical support organisations and regulatory authorities
Price / fee	Free
Lecturers / organisers	IAEA experts
Workload / duration	~6 lectures (self-paced learning; typically, several hours)
Topic category	Computing, formulation of physical problems, supercomputers, data analysis
Short description / syllabus	Introductory module providing fundamental knowledge about nuclear fuel engineering. Topics include nuclear fuel design principles, fuel fabrication processes, surveillance and qualification procedures, as well basic thermal-mechanical and irradiation behaviour of nuclear fuel during reactor operation
Type of access	Public after registration – Access through registered account
Link	https://www.iaea.org/online-learning/courses/1074/computational-nuclear-science-and-engineering

Atomistic Computer Modelling of Materials

Field	Information
Course title	Atomistic Computer Modelling of Materials (3.320 / SMA 5107)
Provider / institution	Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT)
Format	Online course with video lectures, lecture notes, problem sets and laboratory assignments.
Year / period	From 2005
Target audience	Graduate students in materials science, physics and computational materials science
Price / fee	Free
Lecturers / organisers	Prof. Gerbrand Ceder, Prof. Nicola Marzari
Workload / duration	Full semester course; typically, two 90-minute lectures per week plus lab assignments every 2–3 weeks
Topic category	Computational materials science; atomistic modelling; nanotechnology; quantum mechanics
Short description / syllabus	Course on theory and application of atomistic computer simulations to model and predict properties of materials. Topics include classical interatomic potentials, density functional theory (DFT), pseudopotential methods, molecular dynamics, Monte Carlo simulations, thermodynamic ensembles, phase transitions, transport properties and multiscale modelling approaches.
Type of access	Open access (self-study)
Link	https://ocw.mit.edu/courses/3-320-atomistic-computer-modeling-of-materials-sma-5107-spring-2005/video_galleries/video-lectures/

Other educational videos

Video title	Author	Topic	Link
Multiphysics Modelling and Simulation – Modern Reactor Analysis Codes	J. Watson (NCS University, USA)	Modelling and safety codes, Coupling Methods	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gMwIHETxiCc

3.2.3 Manufacturing and joining

Manufacturing Technologies

Field	Information
Course title	Manufacturing Technologies
Provider / institution	Online learning platform ALISON (Mike Feerick)
Format	Online courses
Year / period	Not specified
Target audience	Students, early-career engineers and professionals interested in modern manufacturing technologies
Price / fee	Free
Lecturers / organisers	Not specified
Workload / duration	Self-paced (modular online course)
Topic category	Manufacturing
Short description / syllabus	The course introduces modern manufacturing concepts including agile manufacturing, IoT, cloud manufacturing and blockchain integration. It also covers additive manufacturing and real industrial applications (e.g. aerospace components), focusing on improving efficiency and responsiveness in production systems.
Type of access	Open access
Link	https://alison.com/course/manufacturing-technologies

Materials Processing

Field	Information
Course title	Materials Processing (MIT 3.044)
Provider / institution	Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT)
Format	Online course (lecture videos, lecture notes, assignments)
Year / period	From 2013
Target audience	Undergraduate and graduate students in materials science and engineering
Price / fee	Free
Lecturers / organisers	Prof. Christopher A. Schuh
Workload / duration	Full semester course (approx. 12–14 weeks)
Topic category	Materials science, materials processing, heat and mass transport
Short description / syllabus	Introduction to processing of engineering materials, including heat conduction, diffusion, solidification, microstructure evolution and transport phenomena relevant to materials manufacturing.
Type of access	Open access (self-study)
Link	https://ocw.mit.edu/courses/3-044-materials-processing-spring-2013/

Additive Manufacturing

Field	Information
Course title	Additive Manufacturing
Provider / institution	The Open University
Format	Online courses
Year / period	From 2016
Target audience	Students and learners interested in manufacturing, materials and design
Price / fee	Free
Lecturers / organisers	Not specified
Workload / duration	Self-paced (modular online course), approx. 8 hours
Topic category	Manufacturing
Short description / syllabus	The course introduces fundamentals of additive manufacturing, including process principles, materials, design implications and factors affecting final component performance (e.g. residual stresses, surface finish).
Type of access	Open access
Link	https://www.open.edu/openlearn/science-maths-technology/additive-manufacturing/content-section-0

Additive Manufacturing Architecture

Field	Information
Course title	Additive Manufacturing Architecture
Provider / institution	Online learning platform ALISON (Mike Feerick)
Format	Online course
Year / period	Not specified
Target audience	Students and learners interested in manufacturing, materials design, 3D printing and design
Price / fee	Free
Lecturers / organisers	Not specified
Workload / duration	Self-paced
Topic category	Manufacturing
Short description / syllabus	The course focuses on architectural and design applications of additive manufacturing, including CAD-based workflows, 3D printing techniques and integration into construction/design processes.
Type of access	Open access
Link	https://alison.com/course/additive-manufacturing-architecture

Welding Technology and Codes

Field	Information
Course title	Welding Technology and Codes
Provider / institution	U.S.NRC
Format	Pdf support of onsite training
Year / period	From 2012
Target audience	Students and professionals
Price / fee	Free
Lecturers / organisers	U.S.NRC
Workload / duration	~9 days total
Topic category	Materials joining / Welding
Short description / syllabus	Types of welding processes – advantages and disadvantages; how these processes work; metallurgy of welding; principles of welding design – weld types and designations, weld properties, and failure modes, weldability – why some welds fail and how to avoid failure of welds in certain materials, NDE techniques – advantages and limitations, and how to select; basic codes and standards including weld procedure and welder qualification requirements
Type of access	Open access
Link	https://www.nrc.gov/docs/ML1215/ML12157A580.html

Welding Processes

Field	Information
Course title	Welding Processes
Provider / institution	NPTEL / IIT Madras
Format	Online course (video lectures + assignments)
Year / period	From 2021
Target audience	Master/PhD students, engineers in metallurgy, mechanical and production
Price / fee	Free (certificate optional)
Lecturers / organisers	Prof. Murugaiyan Amirthalingam
Workload / duration	12 weeks
Topic category	Materials joining / Welding
Short description / syllabus	The course explains fundamentals of welding processes, including arc, plasma, laser and resistance welding, with focus on heat transfer, arc physics and weld pool behaviour.
Type of access	Open access
Link	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dMcP3aCHyTQ

Joining Technologies for Metals

Field	Information
Course title	Joining Technologies for Metals
Provider / institution	NPTEL / IIT Roorkee
Format	Online course
Year / period	From 2024
Target audience	Master/PhD students, engineers in metallurgy, mechanical and production
Price / fee	Free
Lecturers / organisers	Prof. D. K. Dwivedi
Workload / duration	12 weeks
Topic category	Materials joining
Short description / syllabus	Covers fusion, solid-state, brazing, soldering and adhesive joining, including metallurgical aspects (HAZ, residual stresses, weldability) and industrial applications.
Type of access	Open access
Link	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XRychX-aR9g

Other educational videos

Video title	Author	Topic	Link
The Status of Steel Production in the United States (CMI Webinar)	Missouri University of Science and Technology / CMI webinar	Overview of steel manufacturing processes, production routes and materials considerations	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Cp1voLBSdbg
Methods and Technologies in Mechanical and Material Testing	Engineering webinar	Material testing techniques relevant for qualification of structural materials (including nuclear components)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=O666-R3N8Qc
Steel Manufacturing – Including Blast Furnace and BOS	Metallurgy Data (industry/educational)	Complete steel production route: blast furnace ironmaking, basic oxygen steelmaking (BOF), secondary metallurgy, continuous casting and rolling processes	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=otVFD09YSM8
Lecture 1 – Steel Making Principles and Steps	Metallurgy Education (Janak Kumar)	Fundamentals of steelmaking including chemical principles, process steps and basic metallurgical concepts	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=y6faVJg2AtY
Steel Making (NPTEL Lecture – IIT Kanpur)	NPTEL / Prof. Deepak Mazumdar	University-level lecture on steelmaking processes, process control, thermodynamics and industrial practice	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CnoVCGx01Tk
Electric Arc Furnace Steelmaking (Lecture)	Metallurgy lecture series	Steel production using electric arc furnace (EAF), scrap processing, energy input and process control	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pDEJOhLje94
The Blast Furnace Process at Port Kembla Steelworks	BlueScope Steel (industry)	Industrial blast furnace operation for ironmaking, including raw materials, chemical reactions and gas flow dynamics	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qD2LPYZjdw4
Blast Furnace Working (Lecture)	Engineering materials lecture (Upendrakumar Malla)	Detailed explanation of blast furnace operation, reduction reactions, heat transfer and material flow	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xRi9eP3uw7w

Video title	Author	Topic	Link
The Six Steps of Steel Manufacturing	Educational / industry video	Six-step steel production process: ironmaking, primary steelmaking, secondary metallurgy, casting and forming operations	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KJL6nPomKJE
How Steel is Made (thyssenkrupp Steel)	thyssenkrupp (industry)	Industrial production of flat steel products including hot rolling, cold rolling and surface finishing processes	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QIF3oSk76Y
Causes of Residual Stress Development in Welding	IIT lecture (Prof. P. K. Jha)	Mechanisms of residual stress formation due to thermal gradients and constrained deformation during welding	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ch_sk1Rhaw4
Controlling Residual Stresses in Weldments	Engineering lecture Prof. P. K. Jha)	Methods for reducing residual stresses and distortion (preheating, PWHT, process control)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pMUFS3pFsvc
Advanced Manufacturing Solutions	Webinar of the IAEA Real-World Applications in Nuclear Power Webinar Series	Insights into the latest innovations in advanced manufacturing from the ISOP Innovation Awards	https://www.iaea.org/about/organizational-structure/department-of-nuclear-energy/division-of-nuclear-power/advanced-manufacturing-solutions-webinars
Welding Metallurgy (MIT OpenCourseWare)	MIT (Prof. T. W. Eagar)	Advanced welding metallurgy including thermodynamics, kinetics and weld pool behaviour	https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLp0pALmMwc6sAERzaGo33E5TyXI2qohr6

3.2.4 Non-destructive testing

Fundamentals and Principles of Non-Destructive Testing

Field	Information
Course title	Fundamentals and Principles of Non-Destructive Testing
Provider / institution	Purdue University
Format	Online lectures / educational lecture series (video, YouTube)
Year / period	From 2013
Target audience	Undergraduate and graduate engineering students, early-career researchers, engineers and inspectors interested in non-destructive testing and structural integrity assessment
Price / fee	Free
Lecturers / organisers	Prof. Luna Lu
Workload / duration	9 lectures, approx. 30 minutes
Topic category	Inspection / monitoring with DT/NDT
Short description / syllabus	Collection of nine online lectures introducing the principles and applications of non-destructive testing techniques used for inspection and structural integrity assessment.
Type of access	Open access
Link	https://youtu.be/k4EhwtvBQXs?si=7m6mkREeMXY4Q3JB

NDT Online Training

Field	Information
Course title	NDT Online Training (Ultrasonic Testing, Liquid Penetrant Testing, Magnetic Particle Testing, Visual Inspection)
Provider / institution	NDTTrainingOnline.com
Format	Online training (video lectures, audio explanations, study materials, quizzes) – Accepted as theoretical education required for NDT certification
Year / period	Available continuously (self-paced online training)
Target audience	NDT technicians, engineers, inspectors and industry professionals in energy, manufacturing, aerospace and nuclear sectors
Price / fee	Paid (course-dependent)
Lecturers / organisers	Professionals
Workload / duration	Self-paced; duration depends on the course module
Topic category	Inspection / monitoring with DT/NDT
Short description / syllabus	Online training programme covering the fundamental principles and practical applications of non-destructive testing (NDT) methods. Courses include ultrasonic testing (UT), liquid penetrant testing (PT), magnetic particle testing (MT) and visual inspection (VT). The programme provides theoretical foundations, practical demonstrations and final tests designed to support training and qualification of NDT technicians according to industry standards.
Type of access	Paid access to the course for a limited time
Link	https://ndttrainingonline.com/ndt-online-training/

NDT Webinar Series

Field	Information
Course title	NDT Webinar Series
Provider / institution	OneStopNDT (webinar and educational platform)
Format	Online webinar (without public records) / expert lectures
Year / period	Sessions organised regularly (from 2020), paid education in NDT
Target audience	NDT engineers, inspectors, maintenance specialists and industry professionals
Price / fee	Free (some sessions may require registration), paid courses
Lecturers / organisers	Professionals
Workload / duration	Typically, 1–2 hours per webinar
Topic category	Inspection / monitoring with DT/NDT
Short description / syllabus	Webinar series dedicated to modern non-destructive testing technologies used for inspection and monitoring of industrial plants. Topics include ultrasonic inspection, digital radiography, robotic inspection systems, structural health monitoring and the use of data analytics or artificial intelligence in NDT. The webinars present practical case studies and new developments in inspection technologies.
Type of access	Paid access to the course and regular webinars from 2020
Link	https://www.onestopndt.com/get-all/webinars

Introduction to X-Ray Emission Spectrometry

Field	Information
Course title	Introduction to X-Ray Emission Spectrometry
Provider / institution	International Atomic Energy Agency (eLearning)
Format	Online self-learning module (video lectures, presentations, learning materials)
Year / period	Available continuously (self-paced online course, presentations)
Target audience	laboratory specialists, researchers, technical staff
Price / fee	Free
Lecturers / organisers	IAEA experts
Workload / duration	~5 hours
Topic category	Online course
Short description / syllabus	Introduction to X-ray spectrometry methods used for elemental analysis and materials characterisation. The course covers principles of X-ray emission, instrumentation, calibration procedures and applications in material analysis.
Type of access	Public after registration – Access through registered account
Link	https://www.iaea.org/online-learning/courses/607/introduction-to-x-ray-emission-spectrometry

Other educational videos

Video title	Author	Topic	Link
Radiography Testing Procedures ASME V	RSA Channel, Indonesia	Industrial radiography using X-ray or gamma radiation to detect internal defects	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tx00RUg1_8s
Ultrasonic Testing	prof. R. Shwab, Ch. Ronspies (Karlsruhe University of Applied Sciences)	Principles of ultrasonic non-destructive testing and detection of internal defects in materials	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UM6XKvXWVFA
NDT training radiography testing courses	National NDT, India	Visual inspection methods used in quality control	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eKRdMQyUDow
Free Training on Non-Destructive & Destructive Testing NDT Training Course	UpWeld -Welding Education Portal, India	NDT techniques and destructive techniques – basic knowledges	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=h5dwls8iWg0
Non-Destructive Testing for Structural Evaluation and Condition Assessment	FPrimeC Solutions Inc., USA-Canada	Advanced ultrasonic inspection method used for weld inspection and defect characterisation	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Wp5x_BasRa4

3.2.5 Advanced characterisation techniques with AI

Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning in Materials Engineering

Field	Information
Course title	Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning in Materials Engineering
Provider / institution	Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur
Format	Online lecture series (video lectures, YouTube)
Year / period	From 2020
Target audience	Undergraduate and graduate students in materials science and engineering, metallurgy, materials informatics and data science; PhD students and researchers interested in AI applications in materials science
Price / fee	Free
Lecturers / organisers	Prof. K. Biswas (IIT Kanpur, India)
Workload / duration	Multi-lecture course; each lecture typically 30–60 minutes
Topic category	Modelling and simulation / Materials informatics
Short description / syllabus	The course introduces the application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) in materials engineering. Topics include fundamentals of AI and ML, types of machine learning algorithms, data handling and preprocessing for materials datasets, predictive modelling of material properties, microstructure–property relationships, neural networks and data-driven approaches for materials discovery and process optimisation.
Type of access	Open access
Link	https://youtu.be/KMO0pXmsyf4?si=1wbaqpx1_SLjilLg

Introduction to Machine Learning for Materials Science

Field	Information
Course title	Introduction to Machine Learning for Materials Science
Provider / institution	University of Wisconsin-Madison Materials Research Science and Engineering Centre
Format	Online lecture series (YouTube playlist)
Year / period	From 2020
Target audience	Students and researchers in materials science, materials engineering, materials informatics and data science interested in machine learning applications
Price / fee	Free
Lecturers / organisers	Ben Afflerbach, Rundong Jiang, Josh Tappan, Dane Morgan
Workload / duration	individual videos typically 10–30 minutes
Topic category	Modelling and simulation / Materials informatics
Short description / syllabus	The course introduces the fundamentals of machine learning applied to materials science. Topics include setting up the working environment (e.g., Jupyter Notebook), handling materials datasets, basic machine learning concepts, data preprocessing, regression and classification methods and practical demonstrations of ML tools for analysing and predicting material properties.
Type of access	Open access
Link	https://youtu.be/nNQToVpz3_o?si=mtxvBfGB6ROmtbaX

Other educational videos

Video title	Author	Topic	Link
Machine Learning Interatomic Potentials for Modelling Radiation Damage	Kai Nordlund (University of Helsinki, Finland)	Modelling radiation damage in materials using machine-learning interatomic potentials and atomistic simulations	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xNNN7-Huzww
Artificial Intelligence for Accelerating Materials Discovery	Carla Gomes (Cornell University, USA)	AI and machine learning for materials discovery and optimisation	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dx9XX-vHtrs
Accelerating the Search for New Materials using Machine Learning and Adaptive Design	P. V. Balachandran (University of Virginia, USA)	Machine learning applications in materials science and data analysis	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-q0Rkj84pOQ

4. Online training to be developed in CONNECT-NM

4.1 Topics

Based on a review of the existing online courses and training resources in nuclear materials and nuclear engineering, several thematic gaps have been identified. While many courses focus on fundamental materials science, radiation damage, or general nuclear engineering topics, fewer training opportunities address applied aspects directly related to the long-term operation of nuclear power plants, advanced monitoring techniques, modern modelling approaches and emerging digital tools such as artificial intelligence.

At the same time, the nuclear sector is undergoing a significant transformation. Many nuclear power plants are extending their operational lifetimes beyond their original design limits, increasing the need for a deeper understanding of degradation mechanisms in both metallic and non-metallic materials. Furthermore, the development of advanced reactor concepts and the diversification of nuclear fuel supply require new competencies in materials performance, fuel qualification and safety assessment. Rapid progress in experimental techniques, data analysis and artificial intelligence is also creating new opportunities for materials research; however, these topics remain insufficiently covered in current educational programmes.

For these reasons, a set of new training topics is proposed in Table 1. These modules are designed to complement existing courses and address emerging needs in nuclear materials research, reactor safety and plant operation.

The proposed training topics are primarily targeted at PhD students, researchers and professionals in the nuclear field, research organisations and technical safety institutions. While fundamental materials science courses are widely available at undergraduate and master's levels, there is a clear need for specialised training focused on reactor operation, safety assessment, materials degradation and lifetime management. Cooperation with international organisations, particularly the IAEA, the OECD/NEA and the Jules Horowitz Reactor consortium, would be highly beneficial, given its extensive experience in coordinating international training activities and supporting knowledge transfer in the nuclear domain.

These training topics will be prioritised based on a survey that will be sent to all members of the CONNECT-NM consortium.

Table 1. Proposed Training Topics (T) suitable for future online courses

Area of Structural materials and degradation mechanisms			
No.	Training Topic	Keywords	Relevance / Justification
T1	Ageing and Lifetime Management of Nuclear Materials	Thermal ageing, irradiation embrittlement, corrosion, creep, LTO	Long-term operation of nuclear power plants (60–80 years) requires a deep understanding of degradation processes in structural materials. Training in ageing mechanisms is essential for safe lifetime extension of reactors and for research related to long-term operation programmes.
T2	Materials for Advanced Reactors (SMR and Generation IV Systems)	SMR materials, molten salt reactors, sodium fast reactors, liquid metal corrosion, high-temperature alloys	The development of small modular reactors and Generation IV systems introduces new materials challenges, such as high temperatures and aggressive environments. Educational resources addressing materials performance in these systems are still limited.
T3	Ageing of Non-Metallic Structural and Functional Materials in Nuclear Power Plants	Biological shield, concrete ageing, polymers, cable insulation, radiation degradation	Non-metallic materials such as concrete, polymers, cable insulation and protective coatings play a crucial role in nuclear plant safety. Their long-term degradation under radiation, temperature and environmental effects requires dedicated research and specialised training.
Area of Research approaches			
No.	Training Topic	Keywords	Relevance / Justification
T4	Artificial Intelligence in Materials Research	Machine learning, materials informatics, microstructure analysis, degradation prediction, materials databases	Artificial intelligence is increasingly used in materials science to analyse large datasets, predict material properties and interpret microstructure images. However, dedicated training that integrates AI with nuclear materials research is still scarce.
T5	Advanced Characterisation Techniques for Nuclear Materials	TEM, atom probe tomography, positron annihilation spectroscopy, synchrotron, microstructure	Modern characterisation techniques enable investigation of radiation-induced defects and microstructural changes at the nano- and atomic scale. Despite their increasing use in research, systematic educational materials explaining these techniques in the context of nuclear materials are limited.
T6	Testing and Monitoring of Nuclear Components	Ultrasonic testing, acoustic emission, eddy current testing, thermography, structural health monitoring, advanced Charpy tests, tensile tests and advanced shape of samples	Non-destructive testing (NDT) is essential for assessing the integrity of nuclear components without dismantling them. Advanced monitoring systems and diagnostic methods are increasingly used to detect early signs of degradation and support safe plant operation.
T7	Modelling of Radiation Damage and Microstructure Evolution	Molecular dynamics, kinetic Monte Carlo, cluster dynamics, multiscale modelling	Computational modelling provides important insights into defect formation and microstructural evolution in irradiated materials. Multiscale modelling approaches link atomic-scale processes with macroscopic material behaviour and are increasingly important for predicting long-term material performance.
T8	Design of instrumented irradiation experiments in materials testing reactors (MTR)	Dimensioning, safety analysis, exploitation constraints, thermohydraulic, neutronics	Irradiation testing in MTR will remain a necessary step to qualify nuclear materials. It is important to know the various steps involved in carrying out an irradiation experiment in an MTR and plan them.

T9	Design of Post-Irradiation Experiments programmes	Basic and advanced PIEs to determine microstructural and composition evolution, as well as gas content	It is essential to characterize the behaviour and evolution of properties of materials under irradiation. This can be done using a variety of non-destructive and destructive techniques at various scales: neutron radiography, spectrometries, spectroscopies, microscopies, testing, etc.
T10	Design of ion beam irradiation experiments	Type of irradiation (light and heavy ions, electrons), irradiators, temperature conditions	A way to accelerate qualification of materials is to use ion beams to irradiate them and determine their evolution. It is important to know how to use various ions to emulate specific radiation conditions.

4.2 Lectures proposed in CONNECT-NM projects

In line with the recommended training topics identified for further development of online education (Table 1), the consortium partners have proposed a set of specialised lectures (Table 2) directly linked to the projects (Tasks) that started in January 2026. These topics reflect cutting-edge research areas in the various research lines of CONNECT-NM as well as practical expertise developed in previous related projects.

Table 2. Proposals from the CONNECT-NM projects

Area of Structural materials and degradation mechanisms		
Task name	Lecture name	Training Topic (T)
NEO4MAT	Design of advanced materials capable of withstanding high radiation damage, as well as the synthesis techniques for thin films and fuel samples.	T1/ T7
EHARMONY	Corrosion science in Molten salt reactors, material qualification, spectroscopic analysis, salt purification.	T2/ T5
ASSIST	Stainless steel ageing and cracking assessment.	T1/ T5/ T6
EXAM-FAST	Mini specimens for Charpy tests.	T1/ T6
CROCODOX	Chromium-coated Zirconium cladding.	T2
EXTEND-LTO	Reactor pressure vessel embrittlement and advanced material characterisation through miniature mechanical testing.	T1/ T5/ T6
Area of Research approaches		
Task name	Lecture name	Training Topic (T)
RAQOON	Raman spectroscopy of actinide oxides.	T5
ACCEL-NM	Data-driven alloy design, additive manufacturing and the use of machine learning in the scope of the material acceleration platform.	T4
CLEAR	Finite element methods and modern digital techniques.	T7
EMUS-TWIN	NDT inspection systems and Ultrasound testing sensors.	T6
PRECISE	Physics-informed machine learning for nuclear materials. Online tutorials for hybrid modelling approaches in Jupyter notebooks.	T4/T7
PSP 8.4	Module on machine learning (ML) methods for interatomic potential generation and module on scale bridging.	T4

Within CONNECT-NM, the further development of online education in nuclear materials science and engineering, with a particular focus on advanced research approaches using artificial intelligence, has been identified as a key priority. This reflects the growing need for accessible, flexible and up-to-date training that can reach a broad international audience, including students, early-career researchers and professionals working in the nuclear sector. The rapid evolution of materials science, combined with the increasing complexity of nuclear systems and the challenges associated with long-term operation, requires continuous upskilling and effective knowledge transfer across disciplines, where artificial intelligence can play an increasingly important role.

In particular, the field of nuclear materials is undergoing a significant transformation driven by advances in modelling, data science and digitalisation. Modern approaches increasingly rely on integrating experimental data, multi-scale modelling, and data-driven methods, placing new demands on education and training. At the same time, existing training opportunities remain fragmented and often do not sufficiently address emerging topics such as machine learning, data management and advanced scale-bridging techniques.

Based on the analysis performed within CONNECT-NM, two priority topics have been identified for the development of new online training modules in this field:

- (i) Machine learning methods for nuclear materials modelling, particularly for the development of interatomic potentials and data-driven approaches across scales; and
- (ii) Scale bridging in multiscale modelling, focusing on methods for linking different length and time scales and enabling predictive modelling of material behaviour under nuclear conditions.

4.3 General recommendations

- Courses should focus on specific, application-oriented topics rather than general overviews.
- Courses should be freely accessible online and permanently.
- Each course should provide clear institutional visibility, including contact persons, hosting organisation and funding/grant information.
- Courses should be hosted on a dedicated website or platform, not exclusively on video-sharing platforms.
- Delivery format could combine live sessions (e.g., webinars) with recordings available afterwards.
- Basic prerequisite knowledge should be defined, with recommended preparatory materials (e.g. introductory courses such as MIT OpenCourseWare).
- Content should include high-quality recorded lectures. Attention should be given to professional video production quality (e.g. editing, structured slides, clear presentation).

5. Conclusions

The analysis identified a structured dataset of online educational resources relevant to nuclear materials research and materials science, including university courses, online modules from international organisations, webinars and lecture series available on open educational platforms.

The collected resources cover several thematic areas aligned with the CONNECT-NM research scope. The largest proportion of identified courses is focused on structural and

general materials science, providing fundamental knowledge on crystal structures, defects, phase transformations, mechanical behaviour, and degradation mechanisms. While these courses are not always directly tailored to nuclear applications, they represent essential background for understanding material behaviour in nuclear environments.

A second group includes courses dedicated to nuclear fuel materials, addressing fuel design, fabrication, operational behaviour and reliability. These resources are predominantly available as online modules and webinars provided by international organisations and are primarily targeted at students, engineers and researchers in the nuclear field.

Further identified resources focus on modelling and simulation approaches, introducing computational tools and theoretical frameworks for analysing radiation damage, microstructural evolution and irradiation effects. These courses are typically oriented towards graduate-level audiences and cover atomistic modelling, numerical simulations and computational materials science.

Educational content was also identified in the areas of materials characterisation and inspection, including analytical methods and NDT techniques for structural integrity assessment. These resources address techniques such as X-ray spectrometry, ultrasonic testing and other diagnostic approaches used in engineering practice.

A smaller subset of resources focuses on artificial intelligence and machine learning applications in materials research, introducing data-driven methods for analysing material properties, modelling structure–property relationships and supporting materials discovery.

Overall, the available online educational resources are predominantly concentrated on general materials science and concrete and fuel materials, with only limited coverage of metallic structural materials and advanced digital approaches, in particular artificial intelligence and machine learning. This distribution highlights a clear gap in specialised, application-oriented training, particularly in areas combining nuclear materials research with modern data-driven methods. Consequently, there is a need to develop targeted online courses that address these gaps and better reflect current challenges in nuclear materials research and the safe long-term operation of nuclear systems.

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